

(Haplaquept) with pH 6.2, 0.829% organic C, and 0.86 ppm DTPA-extractable Zn (slightly above critical deficiency). Two levels of Zn sulfate, 454 and 908 ppm Zn, were used for seed soaking, seedling root dip, and foliar

spray at maximum tillering. The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications.

Rice variety Pankaj responded well to Zn treatment (see table). Seed soaking with 908 ppm Zn produced the highest

yield, followed by foliar spray at the same concentration. At 454 ppm Zn, both seedling dip and foliar spray produced identical yields. Root dip with 908 ppm Zn yielded the lowest. □

Effect on rice yield of nursery treatments at various levels of main field phosphorus

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We evaluated the effect of 6 nursery treatments and 3 field treatments of P

on characters of 25-d-old seedlings and grain yield of TKM9 rice. Soil was a Sandy loam with pH 5.3 and 308-11.4-112.8 kg available NPK/ha. The experiment had a factorial randomized block design and was replicated three times.

Nursery application of diammonium phosphate (DAP) at 2 kg/40 m² and superphosphate + urea equivalent to 2 kg DAP/40 m² significantly influenced

seedling height, leaf number, root length, and N uptake (Table 1). Basal application of 2 kg DAP/40 m² to the nursery was best and yielded highest (Table 2).

The different levels of P applied to the field did not influence grain yield significantly, perhaps because of the existing P status of the soil. The study indicates the advantage of transplanting DAP-treated rice seedlings. □

Table 1. Effect of nursery treatment on TKM9 seedling characters Tamil Nadu, India, 1984 kharif.

Nursery treatment	Seedling height (cm)	Leaves (no./seedling)	Root length (cm)	N uptake (g/m ²)
Control (no fertilizer)	18.1	4.2	9.6	2.6
Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (1%)	18.3	4.4	10.0	3.1
Diammonium phosphate (DAP) (2 kg/40 m ²)	30.2	5.5	13.6	6.0
Farmyard manure (FYM) (50 kg/40 m ²)	19.4	5.3	12.2	3.2
Superphosphate + urea (N and P equal to 2 kg DAP)	28.2	5.3	12.0	6.4
Root dipping of seedlings in superphosphate slurry (5%)	18.6	4.6	9.1	3.1
CD (0.05)	1.5	0.4	0.5	0.5

Table 2. Effect of nursery treatment and main field P application on grain yield and plant characters.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1984.

Treatment	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle weight (g)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Nursery treatment</i>					
Control	8.1	1.9	69	24.5	4.02
seed treatment with potassium dihydrogen phosphate (1%)	8.0	2.1	68	24.5	3.99
DAP (2 kg/40 m ²)	9.4	2.4	88	25.6	4.89
Farmyard manure (50 kg/40 m ²)	7.7	2.0	73	24.4	4.10
Superphosphate + urea (N and P equal to 2 kg DAP/40 m ²)	9.0	2.4	89	25.1	4.53
Root dipping of seedlings in superphosphate slurry (5%)	7.9	2.1	71	24.2	3.96
CD (0.05)	0.4	0.2	6	0.5	0.16
<i>Field treatments</i>					
No P (control)	8.1	2.1	75	24.6	4.20
11 kg P/ha	8.5	2.2	77	24.6	4.29
22 kg P/ha	8.6	2.2	78	24.8	4.26
CD (0.05)	0.3	ns	ns	ns	ns

ns = nonsignificant.

Integrated nutrient management for short-duration rice

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The effects on IR50 yield of individual and combined applications of *Azospirillum* and organic manure with various N levels were compared during 1986 kharif at RRS. The experiment in a split-plot design was on sandy loam with pH 6.8, EC 0.43 dS/m, and 297-18-

Effect on rice yield of organic manure and biofertilizer application with various levels of N.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)				Mean
	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	
Control	3.2	3.8	3.9	4.1	3.8
Farmyard manure (5 t/ha)	3.3	3.7	4.0	4.4	3.9
<i>Azospirillum</i> (2 kg/ha)	3.3	3.9	4.1	4.2	3.9
Farmyard manure + <i>Azospirillum</i>	3.2	3.8	4.1	4.5	3.9
Mean	3.3	3.8	4.0	4.3	
CD					
Biofertilizer × organic matter					–
N level					0.2

^aN was applied per soil test recommendation, with 98 kg N/ha as full dose.

127 kg available NPK/ha. Farmyard manure (FYM) (0.562% N, 0.13% P, 0.75% K) was applied on a dry weight basis at 5 t/ha as an organic source for the main field only. Azospirillum was applied as a biofertilizer at 2 kg/800 m² of nursery area and at 2 kg/ha for the main field. P and K were applied,

per soil test recommendation, at 2.2 and 120 kg/ha, respectively, uniformly to all plots. N at four levels (see table) was applied as 50% basal and the remainder in equal splits at active tillering and panicle initiation.

The effect on yield of biofertilizer and organic manure either individually or in

combination was not significant, but in the subplots, N level was significant. N applied per soil test recommendation (98 kg N/ha) recorded significantly higher grain yield (4.3 t/ha) than the other treatments (see table) and a 30% yield increase over the control (3.3 t/ha). □

Sodicity-induced morphological disorder in rice laminae

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Soils having pH 7.4, 9.4, 9.8, and 10.0 were achieved by saturating sieved dry soil of pH 7.4 with different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate solution. The saturated soil was

subjected to repeated cycles of drying and wetting for 2 mo and then potted.

We planted 35-d-old seedlings of rice variety T3 in the pots. About 30 d after transplanting, white bands started appearing in the upper 1/3 portion of the first to third laminae from the top in plants growing at pH 10.0 (see figure). The white portion collapsed and the affected part withered. The symptoms were minor in some tillers at pH 9.8 and were not found at pH 7.4 and 9.4.

Laminae with symptoms at pH 10.0

were separated into 1/3 affected and 2/3 healthy parts. Laminae without symptoms at pH 7.4 were separated into upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 parts. Samples in three replications were analyzed for Na, K, Ca, and Mg content.

Laminae at pH 7.4 showed almost uniform Na content in upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 parts, but K content was more than double in the lower 2/3 (see table). Ca and Mg were higher in the upper part.

Laminae at pH 10.0 showed increased Na and Mg content, but K and Ca decreased. Distribution between the two parts was similar for Ca and Mg, but Na⁺ was less in the upper 1/3. K content did not show marked differences in the two parts. It is difficult to say whether such localized chlorosis, followed by withering, at higher sodicity is a cause or effect of marked change in distribution of K between the upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 of laminae. □

Healthy and chorotic laminae from rice plants growing at pH 7.4 and 10.0. CSSRI, Karnal, India.

Elemental composition of upper (U) 1/3 and lower (L) 2/3 of healthy and affected laminae of rice variety T3 growing in sodic and nonsodic soils. CSSRI, Karnal, India.

pH	Percent dry weight							
	Na		K		Ca		Mg	
	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3
7.4	0.05	0.04	1.07	2.26	0.38	0.24	0.37	0.32
10.0	0.82	0.96	0.70	0.72	0.29	0.22	0.54	0.45

Effect of fineness and time of pyrites application on rice yield and alkali soil properties

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The efficiency of using pyrites to reclaim alkali soils depends upon sulfur transformation, which is influenced by the fineness of the pyrites and the time allowed for oxidation before mixing into the soil. We studied the effect of 3 degrees of fineness (<3, 3-5, and 5-10 mm) and 3 times (0, 1, and 2 wk before transplanting) of application. The experiment was a factorial randomized block design with four replications.